

THE APPLICATION OF ANIMAL IMAGES AND ANIMAL PSYCHOLOGY IN LITERARY FICTION WORKS.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11448738>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 23-May 2024 yil

Ma'qullandi: 28- May 2024 yil

Nashr qilindi: 31- May 2024 yil

KEYWORDS

*Animal psychology, horse
image, dog image, literary
elements, artistic analysis,
philological analysis*

ABSTRACT

In this article, Isajon Sultan's literary and artistic works, as well as thoughts on explaining to the readers the characteristics of the creation of the image of animals and animal psychology in the works. This article expresses the theoretical views aimed at revealing the symbols and characteristic features of animals in world literature and our national literature. At the same time, the article contains symbols of animals drawn symbolically and contrasting concepts with critical thoughts within the theme of animals.

The technical means of creating literary works and requirements for literary works is to actively and consciously strive to provide the reader with an uncomplicated form of knowledge. In this regard, many reforms implemented in the educational process are taken into account. During the years of independence, a new direction and a new phase of the Uzbek literature began to appear, and his art can be an example of revealing one of these phases. In the works of Isajon Sultan, the realities of nature, the image of rural life, and similar events are written. The story "Bo'ri" is named after Marufjon, and we can witness a specific image of the wolf. The author's language plays a major role in the creation of literary works, which is related to the information provided by the characters and characters and the views expressed by them. But in the use of animal psychology, the formation of literary works, the feelings given to them, bring out their characteristic features, which are slightly different. In this regard, education technology and creative psychology are based on the education of students-young people. In this story of Isajon Sultan, the image of the cold winter life is depicted with wild animals and works of art in the countryside. Said Ahmed's work "Jimjitlik", the images in the works of Normurod Norqabilov are considered one of such image styles. As in many stories and works of art, Isajon Sultan encourages the introduction of wolf images or dog images in his works. "Throughout his work, Said Ahmed remained faithful to the spirit of the people, and tried to copy the people's heart, nature, ingenuity and wisdom, sincere laughter embodied in his examples into his works. Such an attitude to folk art gave a deep nationalism to the writer's works, moreover, to his laughter, opened a wide way to create unique and unexpected images, and to use meaningful phrases that remind of wise wisdom.[1]

It is an exaggeration to say that, unlike other stories, he is intelligent in characterizing his wife, and at the same time, choosing a partner, living life to the end, expressing his feelings of loyalty to his loved ones in his personality, in a way, it is an exaggeration to say that it is a symbolic expression of work or people based on betrayal and poverty in our society. A will not. Animal psychology can also be witnessed in the works of Normurod Norkabilov. In his work entitled "Aqboyn", the communication between animals, the relationship of blood and kinship, the typical description of village life, and the relationship of people to animals are given. The same technique of teaching works of this genre is presented in George Oreol's work entitled "Molxona". In this work, the living of pigs, cows, sheep and other types of animals on the basis of mutual community helps to reveal critical views on the realities of the society in the republic. In this work of the sultan, who creates the symbolic signs of animals in relation to people, this is related to the suffering of shepherds or the relationship of a mother and father to a child. Through the image of a wolf, Isajon Iulton seems to prove the position of a man in society in relation to people. The ideas expressed in the language of the wolf, the different aspects of the male and female wolf, can be a complete and exact example of these ideas. It should not be forgotten that the attitude towards the reader and the disclosure of analytical aspects of the work also depend on animals. That's why many stories and fairy tales are mostly made with animals. If animal psychology is presented in the educational process with interdisciplinary integration, it helps to develop the educational process to some extent. If we look at history, we can see that the issues of suffering are related to animals, and the things that happen in society occur in the example of animals. The symbols of animals mentioned in the works of Alisher Navoi also appear in "Qairar" and similar epics.

Various tools are used to explain to students the development of world literature and national literature and their differences. This makes it necessary to use various pedagogical tools and forms of information in the educational process. Modeling for children: Children learn from their parents. If your parents regularly read books, talk to other family members about different books, show your enjoyment of books, this in turn will affect children's mind and psychology. And as a result, reading books gradually becomes a hobby of children. Reading books every day: If parents spare time and read books to children every day, the child will gradually read books independently. Reading becomes a habit in his life. Teaching children to read is based on the following principles, although it is conducted in various ways.[2]

Literature, the past of any nation and people, which represents the future today, definitely contributes to the development of the nation. In the analysis of the works of Isajon Sultan, many events occur in the image of rural life animals and simple sincere people. Since the creation of this story in 2014 until today, the attitude towards the personality of the wolf has caused warm feelings for many years. In a symbolic sense, the wolf is compared to the chaser of evil among animals or bad people, and it has retained this meaning even today. But it is not without reason that in revealing the personality of Isajon Sultan Bori, who is busy working in such a task in our society, but serving together with his family and friends, and showing affection towards them. The fact that the population lives densely, everyone serves as a community, and the development of land forms in this society is also related to the policy of cotton cultivation. In the past, we know from history that the realization of political affairs and the newly appropriated lands in the life of the society are carried out on the basis of such a reality. Such an event, which causes the changes brought to nature and the shortening of

nature, is revealed through the wolf and a number of such animals. As a result of the development of the land and the evil attitude towards nature, the forms of interaction between animals and humans are formed. Tired of hunger and hardships, the horigan is forced to enter the occupied lands. The reason for this is that the lands where boars live and hunt were appropriated by humans and the new year was opened. Wolves that have spawned in these areas and come back for years cause a little panic to people. All the rifles in three or four houses in the village were aimed at animals by humans...

In conclusion, it can be said that during the teaching of the works, the concepts of expressing symbolic concepts and reacting to the events taking place at the heart of their presentation also arise. Such events in the life of the same village are realized by a simple image style, but they bring out slightly different aspects from the point of view of reality and symbolism. One can witness the information about the appropriated lands in Said Ahmed's "Ufq" column. Directly derived from the image of animals and animal psychology, it is precisely the unique way of reacting to the work in society that creates the unique character aspects. This is also the reading and creation of the work. In Normurod Norqabilov's work entitled "Aqboyin", there are views about the relationship of animals to each other, their place in society and their feelings about taking appropriate protection. Such concepts are produced by the honeys that such thoughts reveal in the form of animals. The works created in our society are related in relation to various events. For example, although the works created about wolves, about dogs, about horses are somewhat different and form the majority, they can be concluded differently from each other.

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